

A new two-parameter optimal integral inequality of the Hardy-Hilbert type

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Abstract: This paper introduces a flexible integral inequality with two adjustable parameters, thereby generalizing the classical Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality. We determine the conditions under which the inequality is optimal by identifying the relevant parameter configurations. Furthermore, we derive several related integral inequalities involving a single function. Throughout the analysis, we provide comprehensive and rigorous proofs to ensure transparency and precision.

Key words: Integral inequalities, Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequalities, power functions, optimal constants.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Exploring integral inequalities is a fundamental aspect of mathematical analysis, particularly in the study of the properties of integral operators and the structure of function spaces. One notable result in this field is the Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality, which provides a precise upper bound for a specific type of double integral. Such integrals usually involve multiplying two functions by the sum of their arguments. The precise formulation of the Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality is presented below. Let $p > 1$, $q = p/(p-1)$ and $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be two functions satisfying

$$\int_0^{+\infty} f^p(x)dx < +\infty, \quad \int_0^{+\infty} g^q(y)dy < +\infty.$$

Then we have

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y)dx dy \leq \pi \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi}{p}\right) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} f^p(x)dx\right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} g^q(y)dy\right]^{1/q},$$

where cosec is the cosecant function defined as $\operatorname{cosec}(x) = 1/\sin(x)$, i.e., the reciprocal of the sine function. The constant factor $\pi \operatorname{cosec}(\pi/p)$ is optimal, meaning that it is the smallest possible positive constant for which the inequality holds true for all functions $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ satisfying the given integrability conditions. A famous variation of this inequality is given below. Let $p > 1$, $q = p/(p-1)$ and $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be two functions satisfying

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{p/2-1} f^p(x)dx < +\infty, \quad \int_0^{+\infty} y^{p/2-1} g^q(y)dy < +\infty.$$

Then we have

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy \leq \pi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{p/2-1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{p/2-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \quad (1)$$

In this context, the constant factor π is both independent of p and optimal. This variation thus considers different integrability conditions for f and g , which affect the form of the upper bound. In particular, the integral norms of f and g are now weighted by power functions. See [10, 16] for the technical details.

The Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality has since inspired many two-dimensional generalizations and modifications. Some notable examples can be found in [1–4, 6–8, 11–15]. A comprehensive survey is provided in [5].

This paper aims to study a flexible and modified version of Equation (1), based on the following two-parameter double integral:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x)g(y) dx dy,$$

where $\alpha > 0$ and $\beta > \alpha$. There are three important reasons for this.

1. To the best of our knowledge, sharp bounds for this double integral have not previously been determined with the same level of generality as that induced by the parameters α and β .
2. This study naturally extends the framework of the Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality described in Equation (1). Indeed, setting $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 2$, we basically have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{x-y}{(x+y)(x-y)} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y-x}{y^2-x^2} f(x)g(y) dx dy = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x)g(y) dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

3. The double integral is relatively straightforward to manipulate and can be used to derive new integral inequalities that are not necessarily of the Hardy-Hilbert type.

These aspects will be explored in detail. Additionally, we will examine the optimality of the proposed inequality by identifying a precise parameter configuration. This includes establishing that π is the optimal constant for the inequality in Equation (1). Complete proofs are provided to ensure clarity and rigor. Through this study, we will contribute a novel extension to the theory of Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequalities.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents our main results, including a key theorem, an optimality result, and two important consequences derived from the theorem. Section 3 contains the detailed proofs. Section 4 contains the concluding remarks.

2. Results

2.1. Main theorem

The result below is our main theorem. It provides a precise formulation of the proposed new Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality. We note the incorporation of an adjustable parameter, denoted by ν , which can be used to meet specific integrability conditions or to achieve optimality. The proof employs suitable decomposition of the integrand of the double integral, the Hölder integral inequality, a specific integral formula in [9], and some standard mathematical developments.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > \alpha$, $\nu \in (0, \beta - \alpha)$, $p > 1$, and $q = p/(p - 1)$. Let $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be two functions such that*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx < +\infty$$

and

$$\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g^q(y) dy < +\infty.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\ & \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

As previously stated, the proof of this theorem, along with those of all the others, is postponed in Section [3](#).

Of particular interest is the special case when α and β are two positive integers. Simplifying the term $y - x$ (or $x - y$) in both the numerator and denominator gives

$$\frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-1} x^i y^{\alpha-1-i}}{\sum_{i=0}^{\beta-1} x^i y^{\beta-1-i}},$$

so that the inequality can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-1} x^i y^{\alpha-1-i}}{\sum_{i=0}^{\beta-1} x^i y^{\beta-1-i}} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\ & \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

To be more explicit, Table [1](#) presents the form for the ratio function of the integrand for small integer values of α and β .

α	β	$\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-1} x^i y^{\alpha-1-i}}{\sum_{i=0}^{\beta-1} x^i y^{\beta-1-i}}$
1	2	$\frac{1}{x+y}$
1	3	$\frac{1}{x^2+xy+y^2}$
2	3	$\frac{x^2+xy+y^2}{x+y}$
2	4	$\frac{x^3+x^2y+xy^2+y^3}{x^2+xy+y^2}$
3	4	$\frac{x^3+x^2y+xy^2+y^3}{x^2+xy+y^2}$
3	5	$\frac{x^4+x^3y+x^2y^2+xy^3+y^4}{x^2+xy+y^2}$

Table 1. Explicit forms of the ratio function of the integrand for small integer values of α and β .

In particular, if we take $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 2$, corresponding to the first line of the table, and $\nu \in (0, 1)$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \eta \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{(1-\nu)(p-2)} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{(1-\nu)(q-2)} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \frac{\pi}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{2}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(1+\nu)\pi}{2}\right) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{2} \times 2 \operatorname{cosec}(\pi\nu) = \pi \operatorname{cosec}(\pi\nu) = \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi\nu)}. \end{aligned}$$

More concisely, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi\nu)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{(1-\nu)(p-2)} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{(1-\nu)(q-2)} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the introduction of the parameter ν , this result yields a more general inequality than Equation (1), and allows for a broader range of integrability conditions. For example, setting $\nu = 1/4$, so assuming that

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{3(p-2)/4} f^p(x) dx < +\infty, \quad \int_0^{+\infty} y^{3(q-2)/4} g^q(y) dy < +\infty,$$

then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \pi\sqrt{2} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{3(p-2)/4} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{3(q-2)/4} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

More interestingly, setting $\nu = 1/2$, so assuming that

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{p/2-1} f^p(x) dx < +\infty, \quad \int_0^{+\infty} y^{q/2-1} g^q(y) dy < +\infty,$$

then the inequality reduces to

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x+y} f(x)g(y) dx dy \leq \pi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{p/2-1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{q/2-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}.$$

This is the formulation given in Equation (1). As mentioned in the introduction, the constant factor π is known to be optimal in this case.

The previous work leads to a natural question:

What is the value of ν that makes the constant factor optimal for any α and β ?

A more in-depth analysis is required to answer this question, which is provided in the subsection below.

2.2. Optimality

The theorem below addresses the optimality of the new Hardy-Hilbert integral inequality. In particular, it determines the exact value of ν for which the constant factor is optimal. The proof relies on two carefully chosen functions, f and g , and some standard mathematical principles, as well as the specific integral formula employed in the proof of Theorem 2.1.

Theorem 2.2. *In the framework of Theorem 2.1, the constant factor is optimal for*

$$\nu = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2}.$$

In this case, the main inequality in Theorem 2.1 reads as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{2\pi}{\beta} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2\beta}\right) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{[(\alpha-\beta)/2+1]p-1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{[(\alpha-\beta)/2+1]q-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

This result is mathematically elegant, featuring a straightforward tangent-type constant factor. As expected, setting $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 2$, we obtain $\nu = 1/2$ and the optimal constant π , as mentioned earlier. Theorem 2.2 is of course much more flexible, since we can take any $\alpha > 0$ and $\beta > \alpha$.

2.3. Some consequence of Theorem 2.1

Now, we discuss some consequences of Theorem 2.1. They have the feature to deal with a single function, f .

The proposition below relates to a modification of the double integral that renders the integrand non-symmetric.

Proposition 2.1. *Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > \alpha$, $\nu \in (0, \beta - \alpha)$, $p > 1$, and $q = p/(p - 1)$. Let $f : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be a function such that*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx < +\infty$$

and

$$\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^q(y) dy < +\infty.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{\pi}{2\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\ & \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

We can also note that the integrand is not necessarily non-negative, which adds an element of originality to the result. In particular, considering the optimal choice

$$\nu = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2},$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2\beta}\right) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{[(\alpha-\beta)/2+1]p-1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{[(\alpha-\beta)/2+1]q-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

The proposition below can be viewed as an integral norm consequence of Theorem 2.1.

Proposition 2.2. *Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > \alpha$, $\nu \in (0, \beta - \alpha)$, $p > 1$, and $q = p/(p - 1)$. Let $f : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be a function such that*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx < +\infty.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu](p-1)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy \\ & \leq \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \right]^p \times \\ & \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, considering the optimal choice

$$\nu = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2},$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} y^{(\beta-\alpha)p/2-1} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy \\ & \leq \left[\frac{2\pi}{\beta} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2\beta}\right) \right]^p \int_0^{+\infty} x^{[(\alpha-\beta)/2+1]p-1} f^p(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

The rest of the paper is devoted to the proofs of the results and a conclusion.

3. Proofs

Proof of Theorem 2.1. First of all, we remark that, for any $x, y > 0$, we have

$$\frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} \geq 0.$$

We can thus raise it to any positive power.

Now, let us consider the lemma below, which is a known integral formula presented in [9].

Lemma 3.1. [9, Formula number 3.246] *Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > \alpha$, and $\nu \in (0, \beta - \alpha)$, Then we have*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\nu-1} \frac{1-x^\alpha}{1-x^\beta} dx = \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right).$$

Using a suitable decomposition of the integrand introducing the parameter ν and taking into account that $1/p + 1/q = 1$ (with the aim of invoking Lemma 3.1), and applying the Hölder integral inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) g(y) dx dy \\ & = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)/q} y^{(\nu-1)/p} \left(\frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} \right)^{1/p} f(x) \times \\ & y^{-(\nu-1)/p} x^{(\nu-1)/q} \left(\frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} \right)^{1/q} g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq A^{1/p} B^{1/q}, \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where

$$A = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)p/q} y^{\nu-1} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f^p(x) dx dy$$

and

$$B = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)q/p} x^{\nu-1} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} g^q(y) dx dy.$$

Now, let us express A and B successively.

For the term A , it follows from the Fubini-Tonelli integral theorem, the change of variables $u = y/x$, Lemma 3.1, using $\nu \in (0, (\beta - \alpha))$, and $q = p/(p - 1)$, that

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)p/q} y^{\nu-1} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f^p(x) dy dx \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)p/q + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^{\nu-1} \frac{1 - (y/x)^\alpha}{1 - (y/x)^\beta} \times \frac{1}{x} dy \right] dx \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)p/q + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} u^{\nu-1} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} du \right] dx \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)p/q + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) \times \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) dx \\
 &= \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) dx. \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

For the term B , we proceed in a similar way, but with the changes of variables $v = x/y$. This gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)q/p} x^{\nu-1} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} g^q(y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)q/p + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^{\nu-1} \frac{1 - (x/y)^\alpha}{1 - (x/y)^\beta} \times \frac{1}{y} dx \right] dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)q/p + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} v^{\nu-1} \frac{1 - v^\alpha}{1 - v^\beta} dv \right] dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)q/p + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) \times \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) dy \\
 &= \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) dy. \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Joining Equations (2), (3) and (4), and taking into account that $1/p + 1/q = 1$, we establish that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) g(y) dx dy \\
 &\leq \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \times \\
 &\left[\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q} \\
 &= \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha + \nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\
 &\left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Theorem 2.1. □

Proof of Theorem 2.2. We proceed by contradiction, keeping the general notation for the first steps, i.e., dealing with ν . Based on the statement of Theorem 2.1, let us assume the existence of a constant

$$\zeta \in \left(0, \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right)\right)$$

such that, for any $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ satisfying

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx < +\infty$$

and

$$\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g^q(y) dy < +\infty,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x)g(y) dx dy \\ & \leq \zeta \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

If such ζ exists, it is better than our constant and therefore calls into question its optimality. For any $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$, we consider two following special functions:

- $f_n : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ defined by, for any $x \in [0, 1)$, $f_n(x) = 0$, and, for any $x \in [1, +\infty)$,

$$f_n(x) = x^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p} x^{-(1+1/n)/p},$$

- $g_n : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ defined, for any $y \in [0, 1)$, $g_n(y) = 0$, and, for any $y \in [1, +\infty)$,

$$g_n(y) = y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q} y^{-(1+1/n)/q}.$$

The weighted integral norms of these functions, as presented in the upper bound in Equation (5), are given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f_n^p(x) dx \\ & = \int_1^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} \left[x^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p} x^{-(1+1/n)/p} \right]^p dx \\ & = \int_1^{+\infty} x^{-(1+1/n)} dx = \left[-nx^{-1/n} \right]_{x=1}^{x \rightarrow +\infty} = n \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g_n^q(y) dy \\ & = \int_1^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} \left[y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q} y^{-(1+1/n)/q} \right]^q dy \\ & = \int_1^{+\infty} y^{-(1+1/n)} dy = \left[-ny^{-1/n} \right]_{y=1}^{y \rightarrow +\infty} = n. \end{aligned}$$

Using these results, the identity $1/p + 1/q = 1$ and Equation (5), we derive

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta &= \zeta \frac{1}{n} n^{1/p} n^{1/q} \\
 &= \frac{1}{n} \left\{ \zeta \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f_n^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g_n^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q} \right\} \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f_n(x) g_n(y) dx dy.
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Now, let us examine the integral term. Using the definitions of f_n and g_n , the change of variables $x = uy$, the Fubini-Tonelli integral theorem, the relation $1/p + 1/q = 1$ together with standard mathematical developments (mainly concerning the exponents over the variable y), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{1}{p} [-(\nu-1)(p-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu] - \frac{1}{p} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) + \alpha - \beta + 1 \\
 & -\frac{1}{q} [-(\nu-1)(q-1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu] - \frac{1}{q} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) \\
 & = \nu - 1 - \alpha + \beta - \nu + \alpha - \beta + 1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) \\
 & = -\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f_n(x) g_n(y) dx dy \\
 & = \int_1^{+\infty} \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} x^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p} x^{-(1+1/n)/p} \times \\
 & y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q} y^{-(1+1/n)/q} dx dy \\
 & = \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_1^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} x^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p} x^{-(1+1/n)/p} dx \right] \times \\
 & y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q} y^{-(1+1/n)/q} dy \\
 & = \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - (uy)^\alpha}{y^\beta - (uy)^\beta} (uy)^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p} (uy)^{-(1+1/n)/p} y du \right] \times \\
 & y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q} y^{-(1+1/n)/q} dy \\
 & = \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu+1]/p} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] \times \\
 & y^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/p - (1+1/n)/p + \alpha - \beta + 1 - [-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]/q - (1+1/n)/q} dy \\
 & = \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{-[(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu+1]/p} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy.
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Now, if we take

$$\nu = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2},$$

we have $-[(\nu - 1)(p - 1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu + 1]/p = \nu - 1$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{-[(\nu - 1)(p - 1) + \alpha - \beta + \nu + 1]/p} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \\ &= \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Thanks to the choice of ν and this last integral, we will be able to apply Lemma 3.1, which will be necessary for the conclusion. Before that, using the Chasles integral relation, the Fubini-Tonelli integral theorem and the relation $1/p + 1/q = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \\ &= \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_{1/y}^1 \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \\ &+ \int_1^{+\infty} \left[\int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \\ &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_{1/u}^{+\infty} y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \right] \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \\ &+ \left[\int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] \left[\int_1^{+\infty} y^{-(1+1/n)} dy \right] \\ &= \int_0^1 (nu^{1/n}) \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du + n \left[\int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right] \\ &= n \left[\int_0^1 \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{1/(nq)} du + \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Joining Equations (6), (7), (8) and (9), we find that

$$\zeta \geq \int_0^1 \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{1/(nq)} du + \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1 - u^\alpha}{1 - u^\beta} u^{\nu - 1} u^{-1/(np)} du.$$

This inequality is valid for any $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$. The inferior limit with respect to n , i.e., $\underline{\lim}_{n \rightarrow +\infty} = \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty}$, can be considered, as well as the Fatou integral lemma because the integrand is non-negative. Using this, $\underline{\lim}_{n \rightarrow +\infty} u^{1/(nq)} = 1$ for $u \in (0, 1)$, $\underline{\lim}_{n \rightarrow +\infty} u^{-1/(np)} = 1$ for $u \in [1, +\infty)$, the Chasles integral relation and

Lemma 3.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta &\geq \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_0^1 \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} u^{1/(nq)} du + \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} u^{-1/(np)} du \\
 &\geq \int_0^1 \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} \left[\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} u^{1/(nq)} \right] du + \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} \left[\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} u^{-1/(np)} \right] du \\
 &= \int_0^1 \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} du + \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} du = \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1-u^\alpha}{1-u^\beta} u^{\nu-1} du \\
 &= \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This lower bound contradicts the assumption

$$\zeta \in \left(0, \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right)\right).$$

Therefore, within the framework of Theorem 2.1, the constant factor cannot be improved; it is optimal. The second part of the proof simply involves applying Theorem 2.1 with the choice driven by the theory of optimality, i.e., taking

$$\nu = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2}.$$

We also note that, using standard trigonometric formulas, we have

$$\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi(\beta-\alpha)}{2\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\beta+\alpha)\pi}{2\beta}\right) = \frac{2\pi}{\beta} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2\beta}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.2. \square

Proof of Proposition 2.1. By the Fubini-Tonelli integral theorem and an argument of symmetry, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy - \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy + \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{x^\alpha}{x^\beta - y^\beta} f(y) f(x) dy dx \\
 &= 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows from this and Theorem 2.1 that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) f(y) dx dy \\
 &\leq \frac{\pi}{2\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\
 &\left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Proposition 2.1. □

Proof of Proposition 2.2. For the sake of simplicity in the coming developments, we set

$$C = \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu](p-1)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy.$$

If we consider the form of the integrand of the double integral in Theorem 2.1, and decompose the integrand suitably, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu](p-1)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right] \times \\ &\quad \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^{p-1} dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) g_\star(y) dx dy, \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where

$$g_\star(y) = \left[y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^{p-1}.$$

Applying Theorem 2.1 to the functions f and g_\star , we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) g_\star(y) dx dy \\ &\leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \\ &\quad \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g_\star^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Now, let us express the last integral. Using $q(p-1) = p$ and the definition of C , we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} g_\star^q(y) dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} \left[y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^{q(p-1)} dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} \left[y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu]} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu](p-1)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy \\ &= C. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Joining (10), (11) and (12), we obtain

$$C \leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} C^{1/q},$$

so that

$$C^{1/p} = C^{1-1/q} \leq \frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \times \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p}$$

and

$$C \leq \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \right]^p \times \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx.$$

This can be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-[(\nu-1)(q-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu](p-1)} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{y^\beta - x^\beta} f(x) dx \right]^p dy \\ & \leq \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi\nu}{\beta}\right) \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{(\alpha+\nu)\pi}{\beta}\right) \right]^p \times \\ & \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\nu-1)(p-1)+\alpha-\beta+\nu} f^p(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of Proposition 2.2 is concluded. □

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a generalized Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality that depends on two adjustable parameters. By identifying the conditions for optimality, we have clarified the parameter configurations that produce the sharpest form of the inequality. Furthermore, we derived several related inequalities involving a single function, for which we provided rigorous and detailed proofs.

This flexible framework provides a foundation for further exploring such integral inequalities and their applications in functional analysis. Future work could involve extending these results to multidimensional settings, for example by studying the bounds for triple integrals of the following forms:

$$'' \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha \pm z^\theta}{y^\beta - x^\beta \pm z^\theta} f(x)g(y)h(z) dx dy dz'',$$

or

$$'' \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha z^\theta}{y^\beta - x^\beta z^\theta} f(x)g(y)h(z) dx dy dz'',$$

or incorporating additional parameters, such as studying the bounds for a double integral of the following form:

$$” \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{y^\alpha - x^\alpha}{|y^\beta - x^\beta|^\epsilon} f(x)g(y)dx dy”.$$

These studies require further effort, which we will address in future work.

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